

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF AGROCLUSTERS IN ELIMINATING THE PROBLEMS OF AGROTURISM ACTIVITY

Jumabaeva Dilafruz Tojidinovna

The independent doctoral student of

Andijan agriculture and agrotechnologies institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8288339>

Annotation. This article describes the activity and initiative of the regional economic development business based on the development and promotion of agrocluster systems, as well as the joint efforts of the business and executive, konun extractive forces, the ethics of businessmen and humankind in the creation and development of agrocluster clusters, as well as the ways of agrocluster development, the economic and social programs of.

Keywords. Agrotourism, agrocluster, innovation activities, integration, placement, tourist zone.

Аннотация. В этой статье описывается деятельность и инициатива бизнеса регионального экономического развития, основанная на разработке и продвижении агрокластерных систем, а также совместные усилия бизнеса и исполнительной власти, добывающих сил конуна, этики бизнесменов и человечества в создании и развитии агрокластерных кластеров, а также способы их создания. развитие агрокластера, экономические и социальные программы.

Ключевые слова. Агротуризм, агрокластер, инновационная деятельность, интеграция, размещение, туристическая зона.

Today, this process is observed in the free tourist zones of our republic, just like that. Such an economic strategy for the development of mintakas means that the combination of small and medium-sized enterprises consisting of the tourism industry and mechmondust enterprises, which do not harm the cultural and historical monuments of khududud, will become signs of its development.

In the development of agrotourism, today it is a time requirement to take advantage of the capabilities of the agrocluster in the solution of bulib, which is waiting for a cathode factor solution.

Agrotourism has been reduced to those following as a contributing factor to the development of turbulence:

- low level of agrotouristic infrastructure;
- the burden of transportation costs in domestic transportation;
- lack of means, places and resorts to accommodate tourists;
- conicity of the state of kup agrotouristic objects;
- the quality of service delivery in all sectors of agrotourism infrastructure is lower than the requirements of khalkaro;
- the load on the infrastructure of quality roads on almost all highways of the country;
- our travel opportunities in our gods and abroad are insufficient data in khaki.

Our studies on the current shortcomings in the development of agrotourism show that tourism should determine the measures that will be considered in the first place in terms of the development of domestic tourism as a network that will bring income, improve the

standard of living, improve the health of the fukaros, improve the health of the caries and young people.

Agrotourism is the basis of economics, the catalyst for the socio-economic development of Khar kandai mintaka and all countries.

Almost all mintakas of the Republic of Uzbekistan have great agroturistic salience, but the level of active use of it, in cup halls, is a link to the level of innovation development of mintakavi tourism.

The innovation development of agrotourism is systematic measures that are discerned by innovations in network development and make a positive turn. In agrotourism, innovation takes the development of a specific approach, the search for new ways to use existing resources in one vaccine with the search for new resources.

In the sphere of agrotourism, innovative activities are integrated into the creation of new products or the replacement of existing products, the improvement of transport, cocktail and head services, the disconnection of new markets, the introduction of leading information and telecommunications technologies and modern forms of organizational and head-to-head activities. In our country, in the following years, the work of certain authors is concentrated on the paths of innovation renewal in the sphere of agrotourism.

Of course, agroclusters are a very complex structure that blurs when it comes to a simple merger of firms operating in the pulp industry, which shrugs off the chukur technological pulp. Enterprises are united within the framework of the nafakat agrocluster, but in certain Sox, Ham continues to raccobat with each other. These are the disruptive power of continuous products and technological innovations combined to increase the efficiency of all factors of product development, ensuring the rapid abandonment of innovations in large quantities.

Thus, the agroturistic cluster is a set of entrepreneurial structures in which the creation and activities of agroturistic services consumers create conditions for rukhiy and khissiy experiences and increase the competitiveness of the regional and khalkaro tourist markets of the world and various branches of the economy of large cities are connected with each other.

Khar kandai the main reason for the need to form agroclusters at the godly level is to increase the racobatbarity of the country, mintaka, Shahar, tarmac and Tabernacle structures at all hierarchical levels. When anicizing the leprosy of the concept of an aroturistic cluster, one should definitely consider these cases. From this, it is worth considering that agrotourism is associated with the level of satisfaction of the client-tourists. In this case, modern agroturistic products are understood not only as nafakat agroturistic Services (placement, excursion training, hunting), but also as the experience of consumers getting pleasure, getting into the water in an unexplored mukhit to a tourist orcali in unusual conditions.

There is a godsend in relation to business structures that provide services - furniture and inventory for cocktails, products and equipment for restaurants, suppliers of various techniques and heads for transport organizations, as well as certain enterprises that are responsible for the sale and promotion of agroturistic products. It can be safely said that the network of agrotourism in the villages represents an enterprising agrocluster.

Practice shows that an economic agrocluster is formed as a result of the historical development of a type of activity in a given deity, either naturally or in a maxad cylinder-as a result of efforts to create such an agrocluster.

Regional agroclusters can significantly increase the efficiency of firms within the region.

This is explained by those who are in tune:

- for them, the issues of coordinating activities in cooperation will be eased;
- the exchange of information and introduction of news will increase;
- there will be an opportunity to use the service infrastructural objects in cooperation

and to train employees in large educational structures.

Based on the above thoughts and considerations, it can be said that it is important to study the economic and social acceptability of the relations between enterprises, organizations and institutions in the form of agrocluster. Therefore, there is a need for scientific-methodical bases of development and implementation of cluster-logical-structural models for the purpose of using them for the study of territorial organization of agrotourism..

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